

The relationship between rural credit and deforestation in three Amazonian states

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Abstract:

The climate crisis is already part of people's daily lives. Measures to mitigate climate change need to be adopted urgently. 22% of greenhouse gas emissions are from agriculture, forestry, or other land use. 6% of Brazil's GDP comes from agriculture. To encourage this activity, banks provide rural credit at lower interest rates. However, we identified some landowners receiving rural credit and committing deforestation. Of 630 thousand rural properties in Rondônia, Pará, and Mato Grosso, more than 37 thousand received more than 17 billion (\$BRL). They committed more than 8 thousand km² of deforestation between 2008 and 2023, representing 8.5% of all deforestation in that period. The method presented here can help environmental and financial agencies monitor deforestation and loans.

1. Introduction

Tropical forests host half of Earth's biodiversity (Dirzo & Raven, 2003), 62% of global terrestrial vertebrate species (Pillay et al., 2022), and play a crucial role as a carbon sink (Mitchard, 2018). Despite their importance, every year, 3 to 4 million hectares of primary tropical forests are lost, mainly in Brazil, Indonesia, and the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) (Hansen et al., 2013; Seymour, 2022), as a consequence 22% of all greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions worldwide come from agriculture, forestry and other land use (AFOLU) (IPCC, 2023).

In Brazil, land use change due to the expansion of agriculture is the leading cause of biodiversity loss (MMA, 2017) and climate change (MCTI, 2022). Brazil contributes the highest greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions in Latin America (Crippa et al., 2021) and has the highest rates of illegal deforestation in primary forests (Potapov et al., 2022). According to Pendrill et al. (2019), 72% of all Brazilian deforestation is due to beef production, and livestock accounts for 37% of Brazilian greenhouse gas emissions (Zu Ermgassen et al., 2018). A study by the MapBiomass¹ project showed that 710,000 km² of natural vegetation was lost throughout Brazil between 1985 and 2017, mainly due to agricultural activities and livestock for meat production. Pasture expanded by 46% in this period and agriculture by 172%, mostly replacing old pasture fields (Souza et al., 2020).

Understanding the causes of deforestation, particularly the role of capital availability in the farm sector, is a task that requires the collective effort of researchers, policymakers, and environmental organizations. In many tropical countries, rural credit is available as loans at subsidized interest rates to enhance agricultural production or support agricultural costs (Servo, 2019). However, these loans may be contributing to more deforestation. While some studies have examined this issue at a municipal scale, few peer-reviewed studies have linked rural credit to individual property-scale deforestation. Notably, recent studies by the NGO Greenpeace (Greenpeace, 2024) and the Climate Policy Initiative (Mourão et al., 2024) have shown a direct relationship between rural credit and deforestation at the rural property level. Understanding and addressing this relationship can significantly enhance public policies to prevent illegal deforestation.

To prevent rural credit from being used for deforestation in the Amazon, a rule (CMN 3545, 2008) was created by the Central Bank of Brazil in 2008. CMN #3545 required landowners in the Amazon to be registered in the Rural Environmental Registry (CAR in the Brazilian acronym) to access rural credit. Into CAR, landowners must register the geographical boundaries of their properties. After July 2023, a new rule was enacted (CMN 5081, 2023), and the restriction was extended to the whole country. The creation of these rules made this analysis possible.

2. Main Body

2.1 Agriculture

Agriculture and livestock have always played vital roles in the Brazilian economy and have become even more important recently. In the last decade (from 2012 to 2019), agriculture comprised, on average, 4.43% of the Brazilian GDP, equivalent to BRL\$270 billion per year (World Bank, 2024). In the following four years (2020-2023), this average share grew to 6.07%, representing BRL\$570 billion per year (World Bank, 2024).

Brazil is the world's largest meat exporter, sharing over 25% of the global meat trade (Heinrich Böll Stiftung, 2021). To produce such a large amount of meat, it needs to feed the second largest cattle herd in the world, where 29% is raised in the Amazon (Zu Ermgassen et al., 2018). Feeding this herd requires large amounts of pasture and feed, which leads us to soybean monocultures used in feed production. Brazil dominates 50% of the world's soybean market, which, in commercial value, represented 14% of all Brazilian exports in 2022 (CEPII, 2024).

2.2 Rural Credit

In 1992, the Brazilian Parliament enacted Law 4,829 (Lei do Crédito Rural, 1992), creating subsidies for rural credit, known today as the Safra Plan. As a result of this law, the interest rates to get rural credit have always been significantly lower than those practiced in the regular market. In March 2019, for example, while the average interest rate on loans for non-rural purposes stood at 31.6% per year, rural credit was observed at 10.8% p.y.

¹ MapBiomass Project - is a multi-institutional initiative to generate annual land use and land cover maps from automatic classification processes applied to satellite imagery. The project's full description can be found at <http://mapbiomas.org>

on market rates, and even lower with subsidized rates observing an average rate of 6.1% p.y. (Servo, 2019).

Previous studies suggest that the availability of capital for farmers may be causing the expansion of new agricultural areas over native forests (Combes et al., 2018; Richards & Arima, 2018; Silva, 2021; Trigueiro et al., 2020). Most of these studies use the municipality as the unit of analysis. Still, they have yet to be analyzed at the rural property level and for a more extended period, which can help prevent deforestation from occurring by denying rural credit to those who committed illegal deforestation. The total amount of rural credit made available by the Safra Plan has grown by an average of 4.5% yearly since 2005 (IBGE, 2023b). Using inflation-adjusted figures, the total amount of credit jumped from approximately 160 billion in 2007 to 350 billion in 2022 (IBGE, 2023b). For the twelve months of Brazil's 2024/2025 harvest, 400 billion Brazilian Reals (BRL) are available for rural credit (MAPA, 2024). Some of the Rural Credit available in Brazil are loans that use public resources to offer subsidized interest rates (Lei do Crédito Rural, 1992). Therefore, in some cases, public funds from the federal government have been used to finance illegal deforestation through Rural Credit or, even worse, to award them loans after deforestation has already occurred. The Central Bank of Brazil graph below shows interest rates for rural and non-rural credits.

Figure 1 - Average interest rate of new credit operations - %p.y (BCB, 2023)

2.3 Deforestation

The agricultural expansion toward the Amazon started mainly in the 70s during the military dictatorship. Since then, 75% of land occupation in the Amazon has been done by cattle ranching (Pokorny et al., 2021). Even though the Industries' Federation of São Paulo state – Fiesp predicted that the demand for opening new lands for ranching would decrease between 2012 and 2022 thanks to increased productivity (FIESP, 2013), what was seen in these years is that the expansion followed a linear rise from the past 15 years in Brazil (Indicator AG.LND.AGRI.ZS) (World Bank, 2024). Focusing on Amazon, it has lasted even longer; this expansion has been seen for the past fifty years, as shown in Figure 2.

These figures corroborate PRODES's official deforestation rate for the Amazon (Figure 3), which has been growing since 2012 (INPE, 2024a). Not all these rates should be considered illegal, but studies have shown that illegality surpasses 95% of all deforestation. (Schmitt, 2015; Valdiones et al., 2021)

Figure 2 – Area of production related to the principal agricultural products and timber in the Legal Amazon (adapted from Pkorny et al. 2021)

Figure 3- Deforestation rates in km² adapted from Terrabrasilis (INPE, 2024b)

We came up with our research question by looking at the figures for growing production areas, growing deforestation, and growing rural credit: Is there any relationship between rural credit and deforestation? To answer this question, we used open data to quantify the amount of rural credit released to rural properties that committed deforestation and the amount of deforestation in each rural property that received rural credit.

2.4 Datasets

Considering the short period of data available for regions outside the Amazon, the study area in this research is restricted to the region representing the overlap between the Amazon Biome and three states that contributed the most to deforestation since satellite monitoring started in the Amazon: Rondônia, Mato Grosso and Pará, where properties' boundaries have been available since 2008 due to rule CMN 3545 (2008). The datasets came from different open data sources. The Central Bank of Brazil provides data on rural credit on the SICOR System (BCB, 2024). The National Institute of Space Research provides data on forests and deforestation in the Terrabrasilis system (INPE, 2024a). The Brazilian Forest Service provides data from the Rural Environmental Registry (SFB, 2024) where the property's boundaries are available. The Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics provides data on administrative boundaries (state and municipality) (IBGE, 2023a).

2.5 Methods

Using a mix of database and geospatial packages² in R Language (R Core Team, 2024), we processed the data sets for Rondônia,

² R Packages: Terra (Hijmans, 2020), DBI (R-SIG-DB et al., 2001), RSQLite (Müller et al., 2001) and SF (Pebesma, 2016)

Mato Grosso, and Pará. To check the results, we used an SQLite database (Hipp, 2024) with the Spatialite extension (Alessandro Furieri, 2023) and QGIS Geographic Information System (QGIS.org, 2024). The main point is that the R scripts made it possible to rebuild the relational database from SICOR, providing a reproducible environment. All steps are described below.

First, using R, all the data needed for the analysis was downloaded from their source and loaded into the R environment. The analysis starts by identifying which rural properties suffered deforestation after August 2008. The PRODES data is always comprised of 12 months, from August of one year to July of the following year. An important concept to understand is “punitive intention expiration” in this context. According to law 9605 (Lei de Crimes Ambientais, 1998), deforestation committed five years or more ago is time-barred, so it can no longer receive a fine. In addition, law 12651 (Código Florestal, 2012) determines that areas cleared without environmental authorization before July 22, 2008, are eligible for regularization. For these reasons, only deforestation data from PRODES after July 2008 were used in this analysis. In addition, a new data format was defined for SICOR tables in 2013, which would require a harmonization effort to use data before that year. Therefore, we used only SICOR data from 2013 or later in this study. Thus, it was possible to check whether any properties that received rural credit had committed deforestation in the previous five years, i.e., after July 2008, coinciding with the CAR registration requirement for properties in the Amazon and the law time-barred period, making the analysis coherent.

Before processing the data, we cleaned invalid geometries and duplicated records in the CAR and PRODES datasets. Then, a filter was applied to use only properties greater than 1 hectare. In the next step, we intersected the deforestation data with the CAR property boundaries, calculating the amount of deforestation on each property using PRODES data between 2008 and 2023. Next, each rural property loan operation between 2013 and 2023 was identified based on the unique identifier *cod_imovel* from SICOR used as a foreign key to the CAR dataset.

Figure 4 - Simplified version of the entity-relationship model

The last step, still using R, was to recreate the SICOR, CAR, and PRODES tables and populate them into the Spatialite (SQLite) database. The entity-relationship model (ER model) shown in Figure 4 was created based on the models available at the SICOR Dataset (BCB, 2024). This step provides a valuable tool for monitoring by environmental agencies and the banks that provide loans for rural credit.

To check the information on QGIS with all table relations correctly linked, we inherited the primary and foreign keys from Spatialite into QGIS using the Discover Relations tool under QGIS Project Properties. Unlike joins where the cardinality is one-to-one, in a relation, it is possible to implement the cardinality one-to-many, such as when a property has received more than one loan at different periods. In the case illustrated below, a rural property measuring 4896 hectares in area in Rondônia state cleared 461 hectares between 2008 and 2023 and received BRL 2,389,297 as rural credit in two installments (highlighted in green). Each REF_BACEN code refers to a credit operation. The credit operation number 509152099 transferred BRL 1,451,424 in 2019 to the borrower.

Figure 5 - Example illustrates the data-checking procedure in QGIS

2.6 Results

From 2013 to 2023, more than BRL 17 billion was loaned to properties greater than 1 hectare that committed some deforestation in these three states (RO, PA, MT). Counting deforestation from August 2008 to July 2023, we found 8197 km² of clearing in properties that received some rural credit in those three states, representing 8.5% of all deforestation. The results are shown in the table below.

	Rorondônia (RO)	Pará (PA)	Mato Grosso (MT)	Total (RO+PA+MT)
Aug-2008 to July-2023	16,822	54,732	25,079	96,633
Total deforestation km ² (INPE, 2024)				
Deforestation with Rural Credit km ²	2,810	3,276	2,111	8,197
% of total deforestation	17%	6%	8%	8%
Jan-2013 to Dec-2023	BRL 41,950,073,486.88	BRL 41,532,067,932.77	BRL 239,336,040,232.12	BRL 322,818,181,651.77
Total Rural Credit (BCB, 2024)	CAD 10,223,232,909	CAD 1,448,876,600	CAD 1,437,907,681	CAD 13,110,017,190
Rural Credit to CAR with deforestation	BRL 5,512,479,690.00	BRL 5,945,328,683.00	BRL 5,900,318,758.00	BRL 17,358,127,131.00
	CAD 1,343,391,300	CAD 1,448,876,600	CAD 1,437,907,681	CAD 4,230,175,582
% of total Rural Credit	13%	14%	2%	5%
Total amount of properties (CAR) (SFB, 2023)	155,507	297,779	177,308	630,594
# of Properties with Rural Credit and deforestation	15,929	13,821	7,391	37,141
% of Properties with Rural Credit and deforestation	10%	5%	4%	6%

Table 1 - Rural Credit and Deforestation Intersection Results

3. Conclusion

The climate crisis is already part of everyone's quotidian life. Measures to mitigate climate change and avoid GEE emissions should be implemented quickly. Denying credit to those who

have already committed deforestation requires no new technology, and it's starting in some Brazilian Banks. However, the Safra Plan is operated by more than ten banks, which should all also adopt these measures to make this restriction more effective. In addition, it is necessary to monitor every property that received credit and identify those who have cleared new forest areas after accessing rural credit. It would be detrimental to allow the cheap capital of the Safra Plan to be an engine for new deforestation and loss of habitat. The proposed method can be adopted as a low-cost and effective monitoring strategy by agencies willing to contribute to mitigating the climate crisis.

Another point that deserves attention is the distribution of resources available for each thematic area of the Safra Plan. We identified that the amount allocated to low-carbon agriculture (Portuguese acronym ABC) is less than 2%. Toward a transition to nature-based solutions, it would be necessary to reverse this balance, expanding the credit available for ABC and reducing credit for conventional agriculture. This would balance credit availability among thematic areas and send a clear message about the need to change food production systems towards agroecology.

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Appendix

The present paper is a part of a broader research. Supplementary information can be found at <https://osf.io/vwfpz/>